

**CONSUMER PERCEPTION AND BUYING BEHAVIOR: A STUDY WITH RESPECT TO
BABY CARE INDUSTRY**

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Abstract

Baby care products are important to enhance medical and nursing care and considerable prospective to enhance mothers' attitudes towards their babies. Assessing the level of satisfaction about the health care products is to improve quality products. Different behaviors have had a significant impact on how people shop and consume. There is a shortage of knowledge regarding how consumers perceive and what factors influence customers' purchasing decisions for baby care items. The purpose of this research paper is to understand consumer purchasing habits and to pinpoint the variables that affect parents' decisions to buy baby care goods.

Keywords: Consumer Buying Behavior, Retailing, Technology, Baby Care Products.

Introduction

Baby care products market in India is fragmented, and the vendors are deploying growth strategies such as building brands and brand equity to compete in the market. Baby care segment is one of the lonely industries that has seen an advanced number of repeat purchases, with repeat buyers accounting for more than 50 percent of shoppers.

A declining population, as indicated by the fifth National Family Health Survey (NFHS) for 201921, is unlikely to have an impact on the baby care market in India. While the NFHS recently detailed how India's total fertility rate has fallen below 2.1 for the first time (2.1 being the benchmark replacement rate), factors such as maternal health, fertility, nutrition, women's empowerment and digital uptake also have a direct impact on the baby and mother care market.

For one, 70% women are now going for an antenatal check-up in the first trimester, which has increased significantly since 2015-2016 (about 59%), while 78% women have got postnatal care within 2 days of delivery.

Key segments of the baby care market - including toiletries, diapers, apparel and toys are said to be growing at 13-14% per annum, with baby care makers expanding their reach and beefing up their digital capabilities. "India has the lowest per capita consumption of baby care products and thus it presents a lot of scope for growth," said Sakshi Mody, promoter of JL Morison (JLM). "Similarly, the penetration of baby care products is also very low as compared to nations like China, Brazil and Russia. So, there is a lot of scope for growth-both through width and depth expansion," said Mody, while adding that India will remain in the high-growth phase for the baby care industry for 10 years.

Baby Care Market in India

The estimated market size of baby products was around INR 15-25 billion in year 2012 and online market for the products was around INR 1.0-1.2 billion out of this. According to experts, in the baby care products market expected to boom and rise at the rate of 13.66 percentages computed annual growth

rate in the years ahead. Yet, the estimated growth in the number of babies of age group zero to five is up to 135 million by 2020.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a measurement used to quantify the degree to which a customer is happy with a product, service. It is a critical concept for customer success professional to understanding and lives by, and it's actually about more than a money-back guarantee. In this study, to discussing customer satisfaction: what it is, and why it's important for business to start measuring. When it comes down to it, customer satisfaction is a reflection of how a customer feels about interacting with brand. The businesses and brands quantify this positive or negative feeling primarily using surveys.

Literature Review

Kanchan, Kumar, & Gupta (2015) analyzed that consumers are turning up more opportunistic these days. They bend to accept changes and look for new and better benefits they can obtain from online retailers. There is huge growth in online sales, but to grab full potential of online medium, businesses need a better understanding of their potential consumers, their demands, reasons to buy online and the strategies to convert physical buyer into online buyer. Singh, Katiyar & Verma (2014) discussed about the ability of the retail environment to convert consumers into buyers.

Their research studied the impact of store atmospherics and store layout on consumers buying behavior.

Kindarle (2015) in his market research report provides a comprehensive analysis of Indian baby care market. It gives a highlight of the major market players and drivers of this industry along with in-depth details of the products offered.

Silver (2007) talked in his article 'Practice prevention baby care products- learning and developmental disabilities initiatives', talks about the products of concern, ingredients of concern, used in baby care products along with their health effects and possible alternatives. Through research perception of consumers and buying behavior of retail in contrast to branded baby care toiletry products was investigated. It revealed that respondents associate higher quality and low risk perception towards manufacturer – branded baby care products in comparison to retail- brand baby care products.

Problem Statement

The industry of baby care products is highly fragmented with wide width and huge depth of product lines including skin care, health care, bath care, toiletries, feeding and nursing, baby beauty and accessories, baby gear etc. The research paper intends to understand the buying behavior of consumers with online shopping particularly in baby care industry.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the changing buying preference of customers from traditional retail stores to online retail stores with respect to baby care products.
- To understand the customer loyalty towards the baby care brand.
- To examine the changing buying preference of customers between organic and chemical products.

Hypothesis

- There is no significant relationship between customer buying preferences from traditional to

online retail.

- There is no significant relationship between customer loyalties towards the brand of the baby care products.
- There is no significant inclination towards organic or herbal products while making buying decisions.

Research Methodology

The present study based on survey work was conducted in Rampur city of Uttar Pradesh to collect desired information regarding awareness and use of baby care products from parents or guardians of babies aged between 0 to 4 years. The researcher conducted study via 112 samples. A structured survey through questionnaire scheduled, developed by the researcher was used to elicit the required information.

Source of Data

The study is based on both primary and secondary sources of data. The primary has been collected through survey method with the help of structured questionnaire. The secondary data has been collected from books, journals, research papers.

Sampling Techniques

Convenient Sampling technique has been adapted to collect the data from the respondents.

Tools of Analysis

The data collected from the respondents were coded and tabulated to suit the requirement of the study. The statistical tools used in study are:

- Frequency distribution with descriptive statistics analysis
- Chi-Square

Limitations of study

- The area of study is restricted to Rampur District of Uttar Pradesh.
- The number of respondents in the study is limited to 224.
- The respondent’s views can vary in future.

Demographic Profile of the respondents

Table 1.0

	No. of Respondents	Percent
Respondents Age		
LESS THAN 30	128	57.1
LESS THAN 40	80	35.7
LESS THAN 50	8	3.6
LESS THAN 60	8	3.6
Total	224	100.0
Gender		
MALE	32	14.3

FEMALE	192	85.7
Total	224	100.0
Education		
GRADUATE	80	35.7
MASTER OR ABOVE	144	64.3
Total	224	100.0
Income		
Below 2 Lac	152	67.9
2 to 5 Lac	32	14.3
5 to 10 Lac	32	14.3
Above 10 Lac	8	3.6
Total	224	100.0

Finding and Discussion

Buying preferences over Traditional and online retail

Table 1.1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
STRONGLY AGREE	56	25.0	25.0	25.0
AGREE	104	46.4	46.4	71.4
SOMETIMES	64	28.6	28.6	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

71.4 % of the respondents believe that internet somehow affects buying decisions. Even none of the respondent disagreed to this (Refer Table 1.1).

Table 1.2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
STRONGLY AGREE	64	28.6	28.6	28.6
AGREE	88	39.3	39.3	67.9
SOMETIMES	72	32.1	32.1	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.2

67.9 % respondents agreed that, people are more aware about products due to technological advancements. (Refer Table 1.2).

Table 1.3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
STRONGLY AGREE	64	28.6	28.6	28.6
AGREE	88	39.3	39.3	67.9
SOMETIMES	56	25.0	25.0	92.9
DISAGREE	16	7.1	7.1	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

67.9 % of the respondents said that, the current tech savvy generation use online retail more frequently to buy baby care products (Refer Table 1.3).

Customer Loyalty towards baby care product brand

Table 2.1

Customer Loyalty towards baby care product brand

Table 2.1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
STRONGLY AGREE	60	26.5	26.5	26.5
AGREE	105	47.0	47.0	73.5
NEUTRAL	49	22.0	22.0	95.5
DISAGREE	10	4.5	4.5	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

73.5 % respondents agreed that, recommendation by family person have huge impact while choosing brand of baby care products, hence loyalty can also be transferred to another generation. (Refer Table 2.1).

Table 2.2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
STRONGLY AGREE	92	41.2	41.2	41.2
AGREE	99	44.1	44.1	85.3
NEUTRAL	30	13.2	13.2	98.5
DISAGREE	3	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total	224	100.0	100.0	

85.3 % of respondents also exhibits that they have fear of side effects of trying new baby care product brand, therefore they are loyal to what brand they are using (Refer Table 2.3).

Organic or Herbal Products

Table 3.1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
STRONGLY AGREE	454	36.9	36.9	36.9
AGREE	634	51.5	51.5	88.3
NEUTRAL	108	8.8	8.8	97.1
DISAGREE	18	1.5	1.5	98.5
STRONGLY DISAGREE	18	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total	1232	100.0	100.0	

88.3 % of respondents agreed that organic or herbal products are good for use as compare to chemical products (Refer Table 3.1).

Table 3.2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
STRONGLY AGREE	397	32.2	32.2	32.2
AGREE	598	48.5	48.5	80.8
NEUTRAL	201	16.3	16.3	97.1
DISAGREE	18	1.5	1.5	98.5
STRONGLY DISAGREE	18	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total	1232	100.0	100.0	

80.8 % respondents shows their interest in buying organic or herbal product as an alternate of present chemical product which they are using, if available. (Refer Table 3.2).

Descriptive Statistics

Data from table	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
1.1	224	2.0357	.73269	1.00	3.00
1.2	224	2.0357	.78012	1.00	3.00
1.3	224	2.1071	.90199	1.00	4.00
2.1	224	2.3214	1.10615	1.00	5.00
2.2	224	1.7857	.61997	1.00	3.00
3.1	224	2.3571	.97371	1.00	5.00
3.2	224	2.5357	.98353	1.00	5.00

Test Statistics

	1.1	1.2	1.2	2.1	2.2	3.1	3.2
Chi-Square	17.714 ^a	4.000 ^a	48.000 ^b	87.429 ^c	72.571 ^a	116.000 ^c	98.857 ^c
df	2	2	3	4	2	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.135	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Calculation of Chi-square value begins by finding the observed and expected frequencies of each of the category. The significance p-value of the table is lesser than 0.05. Therefore the null hypothesis cannot be accepted at 5% level of significance. It also mean that the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

With the help of above analyzed data it is derived that there is significant relationship between customer buying preferences from traditional to online retail. Whereas it is also concluded that the customer loyalty and organic products both plays a positive impact while choosing the band of baby care products.

Suggestions

Some of the suggestions drawn from the study are as follows:

- Traditional market still have deep roots but it has starting shifting towards online retail from last decade. Customer today is inclined towards online market and this market has huge scope today and humongous scope in future.
- Customers need to get more trust on online retail regarding quality and delivery of the product, if it can be solved then online retail will soon overlap the traditional market.
- Customers are loyal towards the baby care brand but can also shift if the better options are provided, for first time parenthood people recommendations plays important role. Therefore, company have to focus on the quality and maintaining standards of product to get repeat purchases.
- Herbal or Organic products can be the future of baby care industry, replacing chemical products is priority for the customer, therefore company shall invest their Research and Development in making a good organic product.
- Customers are even open to buy the herbal or organic product at higher price, which can be the cutting-edge profit for the producers.

Conclusion

Many people are opting for online shopping nowadays. In fact, the industry is exploding with years, due to the potential benefits it is proving to the consumers. But at the same time, buying products from traditional brick and mortar stores is still continuing. Some people are sticking to this traditional mode of shopping and they have their own reasons connected to it. Traditional shopping enables consumers to examine and feel the product before they exchange the ownership of products and money. There are people in fact who go for both online and offline shopping experiences.

With the increase in the disposable income of average consumer base, adoption of organic products, increased awareness of new and advance products, growing birth rate, increase in tech-savvy consumers, modern retail concepts, increase in rate of working women, Indian baby care market is getting powered up.

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